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PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

Xasanova Zeboxon Bahrom qizi

Teacher of Andijan Academic lyceum of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

Abstract: This article is about teaching and learning English about difficulties, problems and methods and methods of solving them illuminates. The issues of training future foreign language teachers in a modern way, focusing on the training of specialists with deep knowledge who think creatively, and are able to solve complex social and production problems, are revealed scientifically.

Keywords: foreign language, activity, problems in language learning, educational games.

Language is a very important means of communication. It is very difficult to think of a society without language. It sharpens people's thoughts and guides and controls their entire activity. It is a carrier of civilization and culture. Today, the number of languages spoken in the world is about 600. They are from each other can develop and form unique family trees. Among these is the German language family English language is one of them. This is one of the urgent issues of the present time teaching foreign languages as a second language and instilling in the young generation love for the Motherland, education in the spirit of universal human values such as loyalty, high pride, and national pride.

Teaching English as a second language is one of the most rewarding careers you could have. It's an opportunity to exercise your teaching skills, immerse yourself in an exciting culture, meet new people from all over the world, and travel to countries you've never visited. As with any teaching job, teaching English as a second language is not without its challenges. Here are a few you can expect:

Lack of Resources

In your classroom back home, you may be used to teaching with fancy projectors, whiteboards, laptops, and programs through the Internet. Depending on where you teach abroad, you may end up in a classroom with little to no supplies. This may come as a shock. It's up to you as the teacher to get creative. Instead of buying store-bought supplies, you might have to create your own using recyclable materials.

Limited Support

Teaching a room full of strangers a new and foreign language can be difficult. Your family and friends might be miles away, and the majority of the staff might speak a different first language. It's

important when teaching abroad not to let distance or lack of support get you down. If you find you are not getting enough help from the principal or head of your division, it's important to voice your concerns early on.

Loneliness

Moving to a new city can be daunting, especially if you're alone. Settling into a new city takes time, and can often cause emotional stress. The great part about teaching English as a second language is that there is lots of opportunity to meet other adventurous individuals doing the same thing.

Language Barrier

Moving abroad to teach might require you to learn a new language. In the beginning, you might find it difficult to communicate with people during your day-to-day. Ordering food at a restaurant, renting a car, or trying to pay for your phone bill can easily turn into a frustrating conversation. It's important to remember that your students feel the same frustration when trying to learn English.

Not Enough Time

Teaching students a new language is a delicate and time-consuming process. When teaching English as a second language, you're always working against the clock. To avoid running out of time, and to provide your students with an in-depth education, it's imperative to carefully plan out each teaching sessions beforehand.

Teaching English as a second language is one of the best ways to immerse yourself in a new culture, and meet new people. At International Teachers Plus, we are committed to pairing talented teachers with top-quality schools and universities across the globe.

If the main factor in the traditional educational process is the activity of the pedagogue, the activity of students in the educational process is in the first place in pedagogical technology is placed. Therefore, modern pedagogical technologies to the educational process of current pedagogical technologies in foreign and Commonwealth countries using it to create our own modern pedagogical technology system in order to generalize and put into practice the works being carried out it would be appropriate to do the following. That is, in the educational process the chosen method should be developed taking into account the knowledge of the students in the group need If the student works creatively through the chosen method, the group is active, the topic can analyze, this is the intended goal of both sides. Science is unique. It is the teacher's skill to choose the technology that should and can be used and relies on opportunity. The purpose of using pedagogical technologies is the lesson interesting and effective conduct, increasing students' interest in science, strengthening knowledge, as well as correct student-teacher relations organization. In order to achieve this result, the teacher uses some technical means or from handouts, game exercises, puzzle questions, e.t.c can use similar ones, but for this, the room, group taking into account the situation, that is, the number of students, their opportunities, and the level of knowledge necessary. If it is effective for the teacher, but incomprehensible to the student or to his knowledge The result is pedagogical technology that is relatively difficult and does not take into account time does not give, so it should be applied in every way technology. Taking into account the above circumstances, it is the same in the foreign language class how many new pedagogical technologies can be used.

Children are more successful when their parents are involved in their education. Parents have to create conducive atmosphere to learn English. Their role is to encourage their children to communicate in English even at home. They should provide English newspapers, journals and magazines to enrich the

reading skill of their children. They may also encourage them to listen to English news and to watch English programmes. The mind of the students should always be ready to learn. They should read English newspapers, journals, novels, etc., as per the advice of their parents and teachers. They should also develop their habit of listening to English news and referring dictionary. They should not study English from an exam point of view. If they study English from an exam point of view, they may not be able to write on their own. The conversation with their parents, teachers and peers should always be in English. To learn English, opportunities have to be utilised by them effectively and efficiently¹

In conclusion, Learning a language is aimed at being able to speak the target language, and the strategies mentioned help learners facilitate learning achievement. However, speaking a language is especially difficult for foreign language learners because effective oral communication requires the ability to use the language appropriately in social interaction.

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